

Table 1. Effect of green manure (GM), mungbean residues, maize fodder, and N application on rice grain yield (t/ha). Ludhiana, India, 1984-85.

Crop grown before rice	Grain yield (t/ha)			
	0	60	120	180
		kg N	kg N	kg N
Fallow	2.5	4.6	5.6	6.6
Sesbania GM	5.8	6.4	—	—
Cowpea (GM)	6.0	6.8	—	—
Sunn hemp (GM)	5.8	6.8	—	—
Mungbean (pulse)	5.1	6.2	—	—
Maize (fodder)	2.2	4.5	5.7	6.5
LSD (P=0.05)	0.7			

Table 2. Residual effect of GM, mungbean residues, and maize fodder grown before rice on succeeding wheat crop. Ludhiana, India, 1984-85.

Crop grown before rice	N applied to wheat (kg/ha)	Wheat yield (t/ha)
Fallow	120	4.7
Sesbania (GM)	90	4.3
Cowpea (GM)	90	4.2
Sunn hemp	90	4.1
Mungbean (pulse)	90	4.2
Maize (fodder)	120	4.9
LSD (P=0.05)		0.4

after transplanting). A basal dose of 13-13 kg PK/ha was applied. The residual effect of these treatments was studied on the succeeding dry season wheat crop.

At 60 d growth, sesbania and sunn hemp had produced the most dry matter (4.9 and 5.3 t/ha), followed by cowpea and mungbean (3.8 and 3.2 t/ha). Sesbania contained 97 kg N/ha, sunn hemp 101 kg N, cowpea 75 kg N and mungbean 65 kg N. Mungbean also produced 600 kg beans/ha. Maize fodder yielded 5.8 t dry matter/ha and removed 70 kg N/ha from the soil.

When no fertilizer N was applied, rice grain yields with sesbania, sunn hemp, and cowpea were similar and averaged 15% higher than with mungbean residue and 141% higher than fallow treatments (Table 1). With 60 kg N/ha, rice grain yield with all green manure crops and with mungbean residue were on a par, 36-48% higher than fallow plots. These yields were comparable with yields from fallow plots receiving 180 kg N/ha.

None of the green manure crops

incorporated in rice exhibited residual effects on the succeeding wheat crop (Table 2). Wheat yield in fallow plots with 120 kg N/ha was significantly

higher than in green manured plots supplied with 90 kg N/ha. Wheat yield after maize fodder was no different from that in fallow plots. □

Intercropping rice and pigeonpea

P.K. Mahapatra, N. Hati, and D. Satpathy, Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, Bhubaneswar 751003, Orissa, India

The response of pigeonpea + rice to varying levels of N was studied in a randomized block design replicated four times during the 1984 and 1985 wet seasons in a lateritic soil of sandy loam texture (pH 5.3, 0.04% total N, 8 kg available P/ha, 125 kg available K/ha, CEC 3.8 meq/100 g).

Pigeonpea cultivar R-60 (180 d) was sown as the base crop in twin rows with an inter-twin-row distance of 90 cm and plant-to-plant spacing of 30 cm. Spacing and seed rate (20 kg/ha) for pigeonpea alone and intercropped pigeonpea were the same.

Rice cultivar DR-92 (90 d) was direct seeded in 15-cm rows in the interspace

of 90 cm. Row spacing for rice alone was 15 cm. Rice alone was sown at 100 kg seed/ha and intercropped rice at 75 kg seed/ha. Row ratio of pigeonpea to rice was 25 and the land area ratio was 1:0.75.

N was applied at 30, 45, 60, and 75 kg/ha; 10 kg N of each N level, plus 18 kg P and 17 kg K were applied at sowing for rice alone and the intercrops. The remaining N was applied to rice in 2 equal splits at 20 and 40 d after seeding. Pigeonpea alone received a single basal dose of 20-18-17 kg NPK/ha.

Intercropped rice showed no response to N. Mean grain yields were 2.0 t/ha for rice alone and 1.2 t/ha for intercropped rice. Mean yields of pigeonpea were 1.3 t/ha for the monocrop and 1.1 t/ha for the intercrop. The mean land equivalent ratio was 1.4, indicating considerable increase in resource use efficiency. □

Response of rice to NPK in long-term jute - rice - wheat sequence

B. C. Mandal and B. P. Sarkar, Jute Agricultural Research Institute, Barrackpore 743101, West Bengal, India

Table 1. NPK applied to jute - rice - wheat cropping sequence. Barrackpore, West Bengal, India, 1972-84.

Treatment	NPK (kg/ha)					
	Rice and wheat			Jute		
	N	P	K	N	P	K
T1 50% optimum ^a NPK	60	13	25	30	6.5	25
T2 100% optimum NPK	120	26	50	60	13.0	50
T3 150% optimum NPK	180	39	75	90	19.5	75
T4 100% NPK + hand weeding	120	26	50	60	13.0	50
T5 100% NPK + ZnSO ₄ for wheat only	120	26	50	60	13.0	50
T6 100% optimum NP	120	26	—	60	13.0	—
T7 100% optimum N	120	—	—	60	—	—
T8 100% NPK + farmyard manure for jute only	120	26	50	60	13.0	50
T9 100% optimum NPK + chemical weeding	120	26	50	60	13.0	50
T10 Control (no fertilizer)	—	—	—	—	—	—

^aOptimum NPK based on initial soil test.

The cropping sequence jute - rice - wheat is widely practiced in the eastern region of India, especially in the New Gangetic alluvial tracts. We laid out a long-term fertilizer experiment on 1 ha of recent

Gangetic alluvial sandy loam, pH 7.0. Ten treatments were tested in a randomized block with four replications (Table 1). The annual cropping sequence

was jute variety JRO 7835, Jaya rice, and wheat variety Sonalika. A total of 39 crops were raised in 13 yr (1972-84) on the fixed plot layout.

All the treatments significantly increased rice grain yield (Table 2). The optimum NPK dose yielded significantly higher. □

Table 2. Average grain yield of rice as influenced by continuous cropping and manuring over 13 yr. Barrackpore, West Bengal, India, 1972-84.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)													Pooled mean (t/ha)
	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979	1980	1981	1982	1983	1984	
T1	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.1	3.1	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.8	1.9	3.2	3.0	3.0	3.1
T2	5.9	5.1	4.3	4.8	4.3	4.3	4.7	4.3	3.4	2.4	6.0	2.0	4.0	4.4
T3	5.3	4.5	4.9	4.6	4.4	4.6	4.5	5.3	3.8	2.2	6.4	3.8	3.8	4.5
T4	4.4	5.0	3.9	4.8	4.0	5.5	4.5	4.3	3.3	2.3	5.0	4.0	4.0	4.2
T5	6.1	4.3	4.2	3.6	3.0	3.4	3.1	3.6	3.1	2.1	5.7	3.5	3.5	3.8
T6	5.5	4.4	4.1	4.6	4.0	4.3	4.3	4.5	2.9	1.8	5.6	4.0	3.8	4.2
T7	5.5	4.1	3.6	4.4	3.1	4.2	4.2	3.7	3.1	1.7	4.6	3.9	3.9	3.8
T8	5.7	4.5	4.2	4.5	4.2	4.2	4.3	4.7	4.2	2.3	5.9	4.1	4.1	4.4
T9	5.9	4.5	3.0	2.6	2.6	2.7	2.4	3.0	2.7	2.0	4.2	3.4	3.1	3.2
T10	2.9	2.3	1.4	1.6	1.4	2.0	1.9	1.9	1.6	1.1	1.7	1.5	1.8	1.8
CD (0.05)	1.2	0.4	0.3	1.1	0.7	0.9	0.7	0.7	0.5	0.2	1.0	0.4	0.2	0.4

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